

Segregation on cold tolerance at the seedling stage in F₂ and B₂ populations of 6 indica/japonica crosses.^a Hangzhou, China, 1985-86.

Cross	P ₁ T	P ₂ S	F ₁ T	F ₂ and B ₂ ^b			X ² c F ₂ (15:1) B ₂ (3:1)	P
				Total	T	S		
Zhonghua 8/Erjiufeng	50	38	17	F ₂ 207	191	16	0.5414	0.25-0.50
				B ₂ 36	28	8	0.0370	0.75-0.90
Zhonghua 8/My 82166	24	40	12	F ₂ 181	169	12	0.0033	>0.90
Zhonghua 8/Qinghuaai 6	24	39	25	F ₂ 184	170	14	0.3710	0.50-0.75
				B ₂ 55	40	15	0.0545	0.75-0.90
Zhonghua 8/Conggui 314	50	31	19	F ₂ 198	185	13	0.0013	>0.90
Reimei/Qinghuaai 6	42	39	31	F ₂ 195	187	8	1.1901	0.25-0.50
Reimei/Conggui 314	27	31	29	F ₂ 144	133	11	0.2667	0.50-0.75

^aT = tolerant, S = susceptible. ^bNo segregation into medium type seedlings such as medium tolerant, medium, medium susceptible.

The *International IPM Newsletter* is published for researchers in the development and transfer of integrated pest management (IPM) technology in rice production. Its content focuses on discussions of current issues; it does not publish research reports. For more information, write Dr. B. M. Shepard, *IPM Newsletter*, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Adverse soils tolerance

Effect of soil alkalinity on yield of genotypes in Kanpur

B. Singh and O. P. Srivastava, *Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry Department, C. S. A. University of Agriculture and Technology, Kanpur 208002, India*

Alkali soils occur more in arid and semiarid areas. Because of high pH values, these soils are deficient in

important plant nutrients.

We screened 10 genotypes (see table) in plots with pH values 9.2 and 9.6. N-P-K was applied at 120-26-25 kg/ha through urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Maximum grain yield was from Pokkali, Nonasail (Sel.), IR46, and IR4563-52-1-1-3-6. Lowest yield was from IR54. Grain yield was severely reduced with increasing pH. □

Effect of soil alkalinity on grain and straw yields. Kanpur, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	pH 9.2	pH 9.6	pH 9.2	pH 9.6
IR43	2.9	1.8	5.5	3.9
IR46	3.5	2.8	5.6	3.8
IR54	1.8	0.5	4.2	3.2
IR4563-52-1-1-3-6	3.7	2.5	4.0	3.9
IR9763-11-2-2-3	2.9	2.8	3.7	3.5
IR14632-2-2-3	2.1	2.0	8.1	7.5
IR19661-131-1-2	2.8	2.2	5.1	3.8
M242	2.5	2.3	4.8	4.0
Nonasail (Sel.)	3.6	3.0	6.5	5.7
Pokkali	3.6	2.8	6.8	4.7
Mean	2.9	2.3	5.4	4.4

Screening rice entries for coastal salinity and tidal swamp conditions

S. Gupta, *Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, Hooghly, India*

We screened 115 germplasm and advanced breeding lines for adaptability to coastal salinity and tidal swamp conditions in the coastal area of south 24-Parganas district, West Bengal.

Tidal water was allowed to enter the plots at regular intervals. The Ece of the soil at transplanting of 30-d-old seedlings was 8.4 dS/m; that of groundwater was 29.9 dS/m. On the commencement of rainfall, those values gradually decreased to a 3.0 for soil and 11.0 for groundwater at 38 d after transplanting (DT). Soil Ece values were

Survival, days to 50% flowering, plant height, panicles, and yield of 12 promising entries for coastal salinity and tidal swamp areas. Hooghly, India.

Variety or line	Survival (%)	Days to 50% flowering	Height (cm)	Panicles (no.)	Yield/plant (g)
Silla	19.1	131	90.6	6.0	5.5
Djambaram	18.2	122	100.4	7.4	11.7
BJN4	21.8	129	67.4	12.0	14.3
BJM5	18.2	132	84.2	11.4	10.5
IR37257-41-3-2-3	37.3	111	96.5	9.4	16.6
IR39558-147-1-3	47.3	132	69.2	9.8	6.2
IR40578-13-2-2-3-2-2	28.2	93	73.8	5.0	15.2
IR4595-4-1-13	31.8	122	78.6	6.4	18.5
IR10198-66-2	27.3	108	91.5	9.3	21.7
SR26B	31.8	110	106.2	7.0	16.5
Hamilton	38.2	103	103.2	9.4	19.2
Malta	31.8	103	98.6	5.4	13.3

below 5.0 dS/m and those of groundwater 10 dS/m and below, from 38 to 68 DT, then tended to increase. Highest soil Ece value (15.1 dS/m) was

at 89 DT.

Percentage survival, days to 50% flowering, plant height (cm), panicles/plant, and yield of 12

promising entries are given in the table. Highest survival was in IR39558-147-1-3, but because of its longer duration, most panicles did not exsert fully with high salinity and low temperature during Nov.

IR4595-4-1-13-2, IR37257-41-3-2-3, IR40578-13-2-2-3-2-2 with flowering durations of 122, 111, and 93 d, appear most promising. Considering the growth

duration suitable for local situations, IR10198-66-2-1 showed promise.

Among four local varieties tested, Hamilton was most adapted. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Performance of early Prasanna variety

M. V. S. Sastry and U. Prasada Rao, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 30, India

We grew 3 crops of Prasanna in sequence in 2,000 m² under restricted irrigation at Ramachandrapuram during 1986-87. Sowing was 7 Jul (normal wet season), 22 Aug (midseason), and 20

Dec (normal dry season). Twenty-day-old seedlings were planted at 15- × 15-cm spacing with moderate fertilizer (13-17 kg P-K + 40 kg N/ha). Irrigation at

10-d intervals was applied when there was no rainfall during the 10-d period.

All crops matured in 90 d (see table). Comparing the yields of the Aug and Jul sowings indicated the suitability of Prasanna for midseason planting. Total yield for the year was 8 t/ha, with a 210-d cropping period. □

Performance of Prasanna in a 3-crop year. Hyderabad, India, 1986-87.

Sowing date	Transplanting date	Maturity	Days to maturity	Yield (t/ha)
4 Jul	24 Jul	4 Oct	90	2.4
22 Aug	6 Sep	22 Nov	90	2.6
20 Dec	10 Jan	20 Feb	90	3.0

A high-yielding variety for coastal Andhra Pradesh, India

P. Sankar Rao, N. Sree Rama Reddi, and C. B. Rao, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Maruteru 534122, A. P., India

MTU7014, a high-yielding, early-maturing, blast-resistant variety, is a derivative of Rasi/IR19667-131-1-2. It consistently yielded higher than BPT1235 in replicated trials during the 1985, 1986, and 1987 dry seasons (see table). In 1987 minikit farmers' field trials at 23 locations in Godavari District, MTU7014 yielded higher than local check BPT1235. □

Agronomic traits and blast resistance of MTU7014 at Maruteru, India, 1986 dry season.

Character	MTU7014	IR64	BPT 1235 (local check)
Plant type	Compact tillers dark green foliage	Compact tillers light green foliage	Low tillers, light green foliage
Growth duration (d)	125	120	120
Plant height (cm)	84	85	86
Panicles (no./m ²)	491	433	528
Spikelets (no./panicle)	99	127	93
Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	97	125	92
Sterility (%)	2.2	1.8	1.1
1000-grain weight (g)	29	28	25
Pigmentation	Green	Green	Purple
Seed dormancy (wk)	4	3	2
Reaction to blast ^a	1	1	8

^aStandard evaluation system for rice scale 0-9. Tested against race IC 9.

Two new varieties from segregation material of IR36

Wei Zisheng and Li Yourong, Hunan Agricultural Science Academy, Rice Research Institute, Changsha, Hunan, China

IR36 has a growth duration that is too long for an early rice crop in Hunan. We used it as a source of resistance

Yield, growth duration, and pest resistance of 2 new varieties in Hunan, China.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Growth duration (d)	Reaction ^a to			
			BB	B1	BPH	WBPH
IR36 (female)	7.1	125	R	R	R	-
Guong jei 9 (male)	-	109	S	R	S	-
Xiang Zaoxian 3	7.0	106	R	R	R	R
HA79317-4	6.6	102	R	R	R	R

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible.